

Near-Field Microwave Microscopy of One-Dimensional Nanostructures

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Abstract—With the ability to measure sample conductivity with nanometer spatial resolution, scanning microwave microscopy (SMM) is a powerful tool to study nanoscale electronic systems and devices. Here we demonstrate the general capability to image electronic variations within nanomaterials using nanowires of VO₂ and Si as model systems. For VO₂ we image the temperature-dependent metal-insulator domain coexistence that arises due to the built-in strain in substrate-clamped wires. In Si NWs integrated into a transistor device architecture we observe large increases in the source-drain current with the tip passing over the wire, correlated with variations in the SMM signal. We attribute this effect to local rectification of the microwave signal by the local tip-sample Schottky junction.

Index Terms—Near-field, Nanowires, Microwave, Phase-Change

INTRODUCTION

Nanoscale materials will underpin a new generation of electronic and optoelectronic devices. Optimizing such devices will require techniques capable of imaging and characterizing both structural and associated electronic inhomogeneities within the individual nanostructures that form the functional elements. Scanning probe microscopies are particularly attractive in this respect as they obtain the required nanometer spatial resolution while providing capabilities for both structural and electronic measurements.

Here we demonstrate the development of scanning microwave microscopy (SMM) to study variations in electronic structure within individual nanowires (NWs) as model systems. SMM benefits from the nanometer spatial resolution inherent to scanning probe techniques and measures the local tip-sample impedance due to the local sample dielectric function. The dielectric function can have variations that arise from effects including free-carrier contributions [1], [2] or phase transitions [3], [4], making SMM well-suited to study these effects on the nanoscale. Unlike low-frequency implementations such as scanning capacitance microscopy, the GHz frequencies used in SMM allow for the independent and simultaneous control of the low-frequency tip bias for multiplexed parallel measurements such as transport or photoconductivity. SMM can further be used to study insulating or electrically isolated samples.

To demonstrate the broad range of capabilities of SMM, we investigate NWs of the prototypical semiconductor Si and the phase change material VO₂. For Si, the high degree of crystallinity achievable in Si NWs enables the monolithic incorporation of p-n junctions within single-crystalline NWs. This avoids complications associated with material interfaces and holds potential for integrated nanoscale semiconductor devices.

VO₂ exhibits a coupled structural and electronic phase transition that is promising for applications such as ultrafast switching [5]. However, the phase transition remains interesting from a fundamental perspective as the nature of the phase transition is yet poorly understood. When heated above $T_C = 340$ K, the low-temperature insulating monoclinic phase transitions to a metallic rutile phase. Due to the change in lattice constant associated with the structural phase transition and strain arising from the substrate-VO₂ mismatch, substrate-clamped single-crystal VO₂ NWs show a complex striping behavior of coexisting metal-insulator domains in the vicinity of the transition temperature [4], [5]. The spatial distribution of the phase coexistence is largely reproducible and can yield insight into the nature of the phase transition.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the experimental setup.

Fig. 2. Contact mode AFM topography of the as-grown VO₂ NW studied (a) and the evolution of the temperature-dependent S_{11} signal (b-d) with temperatures as indicated

METHODS

The experimental setup is based on an atomic force microscope (AFM) operating in contact mode. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the microwave signal is delivered to the tip from a vector network analyzer (VNA), which is also used to detect the reflected complex-valued S_{11} signal. The SMM is effectively a loaded, one-port network, with the local tip-sample admittance serving as the load [6]. Changes in the S_{11} signal are thus the direct result of changes in the tip-sample admittance, and directly reflect the local sample conductivity and geometry. Here, we report uncalibrated S_{11} measurements, though calibration approaches for SMM are reported in the literature [7]–[9].

The high-frequency signal also enables additional parallel modalities via the low-frequency tip bias. This low-frequency or DC tip bias can be applied simultaneously and used to, e.g., control the charge carrier density in semiconducting samples through local gating [10] or provide differential capacitance measurements. In particular, for Si NW transistor devices we can monitor the simultaneous source-drain current to perform scanning gate microscopy (SGM) simultaneously with SMM measurements. We further incorporate a heating stage to control the VO₂ phase transition.

RESULTS

VO₂

We demonstrate the general capability to distinguish between regions of different conductivity within individual nanostructures by imaging the evolution of the metal-insulator domain coexistence in VO₂ NWs. The contact mode AFM

Fig. 3. Si NW device with integrated p-n junction. Contact mode AFM topography (a), together with the corresponding spatially-resolved NW source-drain current (b) and S_{11} phase (c).

topography of a single-crystal VO₂ NW is shown in Fig. 2(a) showing uniform structure. The corresponding S_{11} signal amplitude acquired during cooling at temperatures as indicated are shown in Fig. 2(b-d). At higher temperatures a clear striped domain structure is evident with regions of reduced signal corresponding to the metallic phase. As the temperature is decreased, the stripes become less well defined and the metallic regions decrease in size. At a lower temperature near T_C the wire is expected to be uniformly in the insulating phase, though some weak evidence of domain formation remains visible.

Several notable features are observed in the VO₂ near-field images. For the insulating phase, the edges of the NW are seen to show higher signal levels than the interior of the wire. As this effect is observed consistently across all wires measured, this suggests a physical origin rather than a scanning artifact. Similarly, the regions of metallic phase at the ends of the wire consistently show significantly lower signal than the interior domains. These results therefore suggest variations in electronic properties across these wires not previously observed.

Si

Figure 3 shows the results obtained from a p-n junction Si NW [11] device with lithographically fabricated electrodes. The contact mode AFM topography is shown in Fig. 3(a) with the lithographically defined contact electrode immediately outside the field of view on the right. The wire appears highly uniform along its length, though some lateral asymmetry is seen due to convolution between the hexagonal wire cross-section and the asymmetric tip shape. Shown in Fig. 3(b) is the corresponding tip position-dependent NW source-drain current with no applied tip bias. Despite the absence of a tip bias to locally gate the NW device, a large current increase is seen with the tip passing over the NW. It is also seen that

the largest current increases occur with the tip near the wire electrode as seen at the far right edge of Fig. 3(b). As these wires lack features to identify the location of the p-n junction based on topography alone, we attribute this behavior to the presence of the junction at this position. This conclusion is further supported by the S_{11} phase image shown in Fig. 3(c), where a change in signal in the vicinity of the junction is seen.

As no tip bias is applied to locally modulate the charge-carrier density, the observed change in the wire current is unexpected. Due to the native SiO_2 surface layer, the tip-wire contact forms a metal-oxide semiconductor junction. We therefore tentatively attribute the observed wire current to carrier injection via rectification of the microwave signal across the tip-NW junction. The observed spatial variations are thus expected to be related to fluctuations in the barrier potential due to the internal fields of the wire, as well as the fermi level position as determined by doping and distance to the electrodes.

CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated the general capability to image electronic variations within single nanowires with SMM using the phase transition material VO_2 and the prototypical semiconductor Si as model systems. For the VO_2 nanowires we image the phase coexistence of alternating metallic and insulating domains in substrate-clamped wires. The p-n junctions of Si NWs are integrated into transistor devices, where we find strong increases in the NW source-drain current as the tip passes over the wire, with a stronger increase near the junction. This change in wire current is attributed to local rectification of the microwave signal by the tip-NW Schottky barrier, and may pave the way for new SMM methodologies using rectification to probe the local material properties.

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